

S-N curve for screw fastenings of trapezoidal steel sheeting

Thomas Misiek

Breinlinger Ingenieure, Kanalstraße 1-4, 78532 Tuttlingen, Germany, thomas.misiek@breinlinger.de

ABSTRACT

The paper deals with the design of fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting to the supporting structure under repeated uplift loads. These loads caused by wind or passing traffic (especially trains) can lead to a premature pull-through failure at points of fastening.

Trapezoidal sheeting as part of the building envelope is subject to repeated wind loads. The wind suction peaks that occasionally occur in (Central) Europe are covered on the resistance side by a generalized reduction factor α_{cycl} . The background of this factor is explained briefly. However, it only covers a number of wind suction peaks in the four-digit range.

Both older studies from Sweden and recent studies from Australia extend the knowledge to the five-digit range of wind suction peaks. This range is sufficient for wind suction loads from tropical storms, which were the trigger for the investigations, but not for the passing trains mentioned at the beginning, which are associated with a number of repeated loads in the six- to seven-digit range.

For the design of the fastenings for this range the number of repeated loads, tests were required, the performance and evaluation of which are presented here. The result is an S-N curve for the design of the fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting.

Keywords: trapezoidal sheeting, fastenings, fatigue

1 INTRODUCTION

In the course of a construction project in which trapezoidal sheeting is subjected to repeated distributed loads caused by passing trains, the question arose as to the tensile resistance of the fastenings: The turbulences occurring along and behind the train result in several load cycles, even during a single pass. Over the entire service life of the structure, this results in a very high number of load cycles compared to a structure exposed to natural wind. The cases in which a fatigue design is necessary are discussed, for example, in (1). In the present case, this design was considered necessary.

Failure of fastenings in cold-formed structures under static tensile loads is usually caused by cracks that grow from the hole in the component to be fastened (2). Under repeated loads, the failure mode is identical, with resistance (load range) governed by the number of repeated loads. For numbers in the six- to seven-digit range, no information was available in design provisions or even in the (scientific) literature, so the resistance of the fastenings to repeated loads had to be determined in additional project-specific tests. However, information was available for a lower number of repeated loads, which are presented below, and which were also used to derive an S-N curve.

2 INITIAL SITUATION

2.1 TUDa tests results and their impact on European design provisions

The tests on fastenings summarized in (3) were carried out against the background of repeated loads from wind, in particular from typical winds in European terrain categories I to IV (i.e., excluding sea or coastal areas exposed to the open sea). In the context of the present investigations, these

results are of secondary importance, but they have found their way into the European design provisions in several ways: They are used to determine a generalized reduction factor to take account of repeated tensile loads from wind without an explicit fatigue design.

Tests were performed on strip specimens whose geometry corresponds to the narrow flange of conventional steel trapezoidal sheeting. Both self-tapping screws (JZ3-6,3xL and JZ3-8,0xL with different types of washers) and power-actuated fasteners (also known as cartridge fired pins) were under investigation. The results of the individual tests are not documented, i.e., only the results of the evaluation. The focus of this evaluation is on the resistance to 5000 repeated loads, as it is assumed for the above-mentioned terrain categories that the characteristic wind loads act approximately 5000 times during the 50-year service life – an assumption that deviates from EN 1991-1-4 (4), Annex B.3, stating that the characteristic wind loads act just once over the service life. Nevertheless, the 5000 load cycles have since been adopted in many documents, e.g., in (5). It is also noted in (3) that the number of load cycles to be assumed for the determination of the reduction factor for the resistance does not pose a major statistical uncertainty, as the resistance to repeated loads hardly changes with the range of the number of cycles under consideration.

Failure mode for static and repeated loads is identical, thus, presentation is based on a ratio of resistance to repeated loads (more precisely: applied load range) to resistance to static loads:

$$\Delta f_{p,Rk} = \frac{\Delta F_{p,Rk}}{F_{p,Rk}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta F_{p,Rk}$ is the resistance to repeated tensile loads expressed as applied load range

$F_{p,Rk}$ is the resistance to static tensile loads

At $N = 5000$ load cycles, screw fastening of sheet metal with $t_1 \geq 0.75$ mm resulted in ratios between $\Delta f_p = 0.40$ and 0.55 . For $t_1 < 0.75$ mm (and also power-actuated fasteners), the ratio decreased to $\Delta f_p = 0.3$. Taking into account the different safety concepts for static loads and repeated loads, the sought reduction factor resulted from a ratio of the resistance to repeated loads to the resistance to static loads of 0.40 : Based on a global partial factor against failure under static loads of $\gamma_F \cdot \gamma_M = 1.5 \cdot 1.33 = 2.0$ and against failure under repeated loads of $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.3$, a reduction of the 5% fractile values determined in the static tests in the form

$$\alpha_{cycl} = \frac{\Delta F_{p,Rk} / \gamma_{Mf}}{F_{p,Rk} / \gamma_M \cdot \gamma_F} \approx \Delta f_p \cdot \gamma_F \approx 0.4 \cdot 1.5 = 0.6 \approx \frac{2}{3} \quad (2)$$

where γ_{Mf} partial factor for resistance in fatigue design

γ_M partial factor for resistance in static design

γ_F partial factor for actions, 1.5 for wind loads

is required. For screw fastenings, this reduction factor has found its way into (5), (6), and (7). However, it should not be concealed that both in the first edition to (6) and in (8) a reduction factor $\alpha_{cycl} = 1/2$, see (2). This would be more in line with $\Delta f_p = 0.3$ determined for $t_1 < 0.75$ mm. And if different partial factors γ_{Mf} and γ_M are provided for repeated loads and static loads, α_{cycl} also changes: The partial factor $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.33$ assumed in (3) corresponds approximately to that assumed in (9) for a safe life design concept with high consequences of failure. On the other corner of the spectrum (and of the table with partial factors), $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.00$ applies for a damage-tolerant design concept with low consequences. This results in

$$\alpha_{cycl} = \Delta f_p \cdot \frac{\gamma_M \cdot \gamma_F}{\gamma_{Mf}} \approx 0.4 \cdot \frac{1.33 \cdot 1.5}{1.00} = 0.80 \quad (3)$$

2.2 KTH test results by B. Nissfolk

The tests on fastenings summarized in (10) were carried out – as part of a larger research project at the Kungliga Tekniska högskolan (KTH) – against the background of repeated loads from wind.

However, the number of repeated loads investigated is in ranges that are significantly higher than those on which not only (3) is based. This proves to be a fortunate coincidence, because in the context of the present investigations, these results are important because they capture the finite life region.

Tests were basically performed on trapezoidal steel sheeting DO-TP 120 made of steel SIS 14 21 22 ($R_m = 500 \text{ N/mm}^2$) of sheet thickness $t_1 = 0.65 \text{ mm}$, in a few cases also on trapezoidal steel sheeting TRP 110 also made of steel SIS 14 21 22 ($R_m = 508 \text{ N/mm}^2$), but of sheet thickness $t_1 = 0.58 \text{ mm}$ (i.e., in any case with sheet thicknesses $< 0.75 \text{ mm}$, for which according to (3) a lower resistance to repeated loads is assumed). Also, tests with trapezoidal aluminium sheeting were performed, but these have not been considered here. The test setup corresponded to that given in (6). Self-tapping screws 6,2xL with washers E14 were used in the tests. Although failure modes both in the tests under static and repeated loads are identical, evaluation in (10) is based on the absolute values of the load range and maximum load. The results of this evaluation are two S-N curves: One based on crack initiation, the other based on complete pull-through failure.

2.3 Pražské test results by M. Strnad

The tests on fastenings summarized in (11) were carried out against the background of repeated loads from wind. In the context of the present investigations, these results are of secondary importance due to incomplete information.

Tests were performed on strip specimens whose geometry corresponds to the internal flange of a hat-section. Self-tapping screws 6,3xL with washers S17 were under investigation. The results of the individual tests are not documented, i.e., only the results of the evaluation in the form of a mean value S-N curve. This is based on the absolute values of the load range. As no information is provided on the resistance to static loads, it is not possible to convert this into a curve based on ratios. In (12), which can be seen as a continuation of (11), there is a reference to an earlier (unavailable) paper (13) by the same author. According to the reference, he also worked with ratios in (13). In (12) there is also the statement that resistance to repeated loads is “influenced by a great variety of fastening parameters” and that it is “better to test each configuration separately, rather than to set up complicated formulae”.

2.4 QUT test results by M. Kathekeyan

The tests on fastenings documented in (14) were carried out against the background of repeated loads from wind, in particular from strong wind events (tropical cyclone in the Australian region). Accordingly, the focus was placed on the area of low-cycle fatigue (LCF) up to finite life resistance. In the context of the present investigations, these results are important because they capture the transition from resistance to static loads to fatigue strength under repeated loads.

Tests were performed on hat sections (with two lip-stiffened free flanges) made of steel G300 ($R_m = 315 \text{ N/mm}^2$ to 350 N/mm^2) and G550 ($R_m = 615 \text{ N/mm}^2$ to 660 N/mm^2) of sheet thickness 0.75 mm to 1.00 mm. The hat sections are fastened using self-drilling screws 4.8xL or 5.5xL (with 11 mm or 14.5 mm collar diameter) and arranged in pairs on the two free flanges. The load introduction into the screw was thus slightly eccentric. As failure mode both in the tests under static and repeated loads is identical, evaluation in (14) is based on the ratio of the applied load range to the resistance to static load. The results of this evaluation are two S-N curves: One based on crack initiation, the other based on complete pull-through failure. Both form a horizontal plateau with $\Delta f_p = 0.40$ at just over $1 \cdot 10^4$ load cycles.

3 ADDITIONAL PROJECT-SPECIFIC TESTS

The available results are not sufficient for an extrapolation into the six- or even seven-digit range of the number of load cycles, so additional tests became necessary. These additional tests with a lower load range and thus a higher number of load cycles were performed by H. Eirich at KIT and are documented in (15). The test specimens (trapezoidal steel sheeting 50/250/1.50 and self-tapping thread-forming screw JZ1-6.3xL-E22) were chosen project-specifically.

The screws used required pre-drilling. Due to the small thickness of the sheeting to be fastened, the hole is not exactly circular, see *Fig. 1a*). Comparable figures of holes can be found in (10), therefore, this was classified as typical for the application and accepted as an “initial imperfection”.

Fig. 1. a) Drill hole; b) Crack pattern (source: Hans Eirich, KIT 2022)

The test setup corresponded to that given in (6) with $l_1 = 1000$ mm and $l_2 = 500$ mm, see *Fig. 2*.

Fig. 2. View and sections of the test set-up

The first tests were performed with static loads, whose results then served as a reference. The tests with repeated loads were carried out with two comparatively low relative load ranges of $\Delta f_{p,2} = 0.0394$ ($\Delta F_{p,2} = 0.45$ kN) and $\Delta f_{p,3} = 0.0788$ ($\Delta F_{p,3} = 0.90$ kN), i.e., with approx. 4% and 8% of the resistance obtained from the tests with static loads ($F_{p,mean} = 11.43$ kN): Against the background of the present test results from (14) covering the area of low-cycle fatigue (LCF) up to finite life resistance to repeated loads, the focus of the tests was placed on determining the constant amplitude fatigue limit.

The tests with a load range $\Delta f_{p,2} = 0.0394$ were terminated after $5 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles without failure. Tests with load range $\Delta f_{p,3} = 0.0788$ failed after $N_{3,i} = 2.85 \cdot 10^5$ to $1.09 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles, i.e., showed a considerable (but expected) scatter in results. Failure always occurred due to the formation of cracks in the trapezoidal sheeting, see *Fig. 1b*).

4 DERIVATION OF AN S-N CURVE FOR TENSILE-LOADED SCREW FASTENINGS

4.1 Finite life region

The evaluation of the tests is based on the method described in (16), which is also the basis of prEN 1993-1-9 (9). The method according to (16) assumes that the slope parameter m_1 is known. This is not the case here. The first step is therefore to determine the slope as a mean value curve. For this purpose, only the tests from (10), (14) and the tests from (15), in which a failure occurred (load range $\Delta f_{p,3}$), are taken into account. The sheet thickness range covered by this is $t_1 = 0.58$ mm to $t_1 = 1.5$ mm, i.e., no differentiation is made between $t_1 < 0.75$ mm and $t_1 \geq 0.75$ mm. The test results and the resulting slope are shown in *Fig. 3*. Instead of stress ranges $\Delta \sigma$, ratios Δf_p of the applied load range to resistance to static loads are plotted on the ordinate axis, adopting the principle already used in (3) and in (14):

$$\Delta f_{p,i} = \frac{\Delta F_{p,i}}{F_{p,mean}} \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta F_{p,i}$ is the applied load range

$F_{p,mean}$ is the mean resistance to static tensile loads

This ratio takes into account not only the influence of the sheet thicknesses already mentioned above but also other dimensions such as the dimensions of the fastened sheeting or the diameter of the washer or collar. Nevertheless, certain “groups” can be seen, i.e., the influence of these parameters does not completely disappear. For example, the results of the tests from (10) with small sheet thicknesses tend to be further to the left. On the other hand, some of the tests from (15) with the large sheet thickness $t_1 = 1.50$ mm are similarly far to the left.

Fig. 3. Slope of the S-N curve for tensile-loaded screw fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting

In prEN 1993-1-9 (9), the slope parameter m_1 is defined as a function of the notch-geometric and material effects. For non-welded details with a slight notch effect, $m_1 = 5$ applies; for details with a strong notch effect, $m_1 = 3$ applies. In this respect, the result $m_1 = 2.72$ is plausible, as the fastening detail under consideration must be regarded as a detail with a strong notch effect due to drilling and thread forming, including imperfections as shown in Fig. 1a). The two processes presumably have a notch effect that is even more pronounced than those on which the details according to prEN 1993-1-9 (which after all require a surface condition according to EXC3) are based.

The slope parameter $m_1 = 2.72$ leads to

$$\log \hat{a} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \left(\sum \log N_i + m_1 \cdot \sum \log \Delta f_{p,i} \right) = 2.936 \quad (5)$$

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum \left[\log N_i - \left(\log \hat{a} - m_1 \cdot \log \Delta f_{p,i} \right) \right]^2}{n-1}} = 0.346 \quad (1)$$

$$\log a_k = \log \hat{a} - k_n \cdot s = 2.351 \quad (6)$$

For the $N = N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles characterising an S-N curve, this results in

$$\log \Delta f_{p,C} = \frac{\log 2 \cdot 10^6 - \log a_k}{-m_1} = -1.454 \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta f_{p,C} = 10^{\log \Delta f_{p,C}} = 0.035 \quad (8)$$

and the S-N curve labelled in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Discussion of the S-N curves for tensile-loaded screw fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting

For the number of $N = 5000$ repeated loads on which the reduction factor $\alpha_{cycl} = 2/3$ according to (5), (6), and (7) is based, the S-N curve gives $\Delta f_p = 0.32$. By including the small sheet thicknesses investigated in (10), the resistance is inevitably closer to the value given in (3) for $t_1 < 0.75$ mm. In view of the wide range of applications for the S-N curve developed here, however, this is to be appreciated.

A deviating S-N curve for the finite life region was defined for the project initiating the present investigations. Due to the high number of repeated loads occurring there and the known large sheet thickness $t_1 = 1.50$ mm, the tests with $t_1 < 0.75$ mm were not taken into account, and the number $N_{3,k}$ of repeated loads resulting from a statistical evaluation of the results for $\Delta f_{p,3} = 0.0788$ was defined as a constraint point. With $m_1 = 2.67$, the resulting slope was practically identical. Due to the constraint point, the S-N curve shifted slightly further to the left, resulting in $\Delta f_{p,C} = 0.030$ for $N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$.

4.2 Infinite life region

For a constant amplitude load, $N_D = N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ is defined as the fatigue limit. An extension of the S-N curve with $m_1 = 2.72$ to $N = 5 \cdot 10^6$ and thus to an ever-lower CAFL does not appear justified in view of the number of load cycles achieved for $\Delta f_{p,2} = 0.039$ (tests terminated at $5 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles without failure). Therefore, $\Delta f_{p,D} = \Delta f_{p,C} = 0.035$ applies.

4.3 Extended fatigue resistance curve

The decrease in fatigue strength at load ranges above and below the CAFL is calculated in accordance with (9) and Haibach using

$$m_2 = 2 \cdot m_1 - 1 = 4.43 \quad (9)$$

The variable amplitude fatigue limit at $N_L = 10^8$ repeated loads thus becomes

$$\Delta f_{p,L} = \Delta f_{p,D} \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot 10^6}{10^8} \right)^{\frac{1}{m_2}} = 0.0145 \quad (10)$$

4.4 Partial factors

The role of the partial factor has already been discussed in section 2.1 in connection with (3). In (5), a design service life of 25 years is assumed for the fastenings. However, the tendency is to assume a design service life of 50 years for sheeting, i.e., the same service life as for the structure itself. In this respect, the partial factor should be based on a safe life design concept. Taking into account the definition of the structural classes in (7), this results in the following recommendation for the partial factors:

SC I – high consequences – $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.35$ (or $\gamma_{Mf} = \gamma_M = 1.33$)

SC II – medium to high consequences – $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.25$ to 1.35

SC III – structural – low to medium consequences – $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.15$ to 1.25

SC III – non-structural – low consequences – $\gamma_{Mf} = 1.15$

However, this differentiation questions the use of a generalized (i.e. constant) reduction factor α_{cycl} in a simplified design to repeated loads from wind without an explicit fatigue design.

5 FURTHER ASPECTS

5.1 Loosening of screws

The screws used in cold-formed structures are self-tapping thread-forming screws, which create their thread not by cutting but by deformation, i.e., compaction and displacement of the material in the drilled hole (if these screws are provided with a drill point, the drill hole is also produced by the screw). The resulting very distinct form fit and the friction forces resulting from "preload by compaction" ensure that the screw is secured against loosening (17).

Conversely, this results in the requirement for a minimum thickness of the supporting structure, which depends on the thread's pitch. If this is not given (e.g., in the case of seam fasteners between two sheeting panels), securing against loosening must be achieved in another way, e.g., by ensuring that after tightening both components to be joined come to rest in a (thread-free) undercut. Flow-drilling screws produce the required minimum thickness by flaring the material around the drilled hole and forming the thread in the protruding material.

5.2 S-N Curve for shear-loaded screw fastenings

Although no repeated shear loads were applied to the fastenings in the project initiating the present investigations, a brief look at their behaviour under this load should be taken here. Even if these do not lead to a definitive proposal for an S-N curve, some interesting conclusions can be drawn.

Repeated shear loads in fastenings have already been addressed in (3). However, the approach of a reduction factor was not pursued further, i.e., no reduction was applied: First, it is assumed that the temperature loads acting with significantly more than 5000 cycles result in the formation of elongated holes, so that constraining forces from temperature do not occur repeatedly. This means that there are only repeated loads from natural wind, for which again a number of 5000 repeated loads were assumed. For this small number, the resistance to repeated shear loads (applied load range) is more than 80% of the resistance to static shear loads (whereby in this case, the failure modes differ: net-section failure and shear failure of the fastener itself under repeated shear loads compared to elongation of holes and tilting under static load).

As a part of the already introduced research project at KTH, tests were also performed on fastenings under repeated shear loads. Three series with varying thicknesses of component I, but constant thickness $t_{II} = 3.06$ mm of component II, were investigated. As with the tensile-loaded fastenings, self-tapping screws 6.2xL were used in the tests. The results are documented in (10).

Repeated shear loads in fastenings have also been addressed in (11) and (12), but unfortunately, no results of individual tests are documented, i.e. only the results of the evaluation in the form of a mean value S-N curve.

Tests on fastenings with self-tapping screws under repeated shear loads are documented in (18). Two sheet thickness combinations (but t_I kept constant) were examined. Self-tapping screws 4.8xL were used for the tests.

Again, an evaluation based on the ratio of the applied load range to resistance to static loads was used. As the latter is more difficult to define for fastenings under shear loads and the failure modes vary, this procedure should probably be critically scrutinized here. Fig. 5 shows the determination of the slope of the S-N curve for the screw fastenings.

Fig. 5. Slope of the S-N curve for shear-loaded screw and riveted fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting

The first noticeable is the large scatter in results. The issue of failure mode is likely to play a role here. And not only the already mentioned different failure modes under repeated and static loads, but also the basic definition of the failure mode (see also (3)). In addition, the geometry of the specimens is probably not insignificant, e.g., the width of the strips used in the tests and whether there are one or – as in (10) – two rows of screws. The large slope parameter $m_1 = 20.7$ of the curve is also remarkable, something that was already noticed in (3).

Fig. 6. Finite life region of the S-N curve for shear-loaded screw fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting

The statistical evaluation analogous to that in section 4.1 results for shear-loaded screw fastenings in $\Delta f_{v,C} = 0.300$ at $N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ repeated shear loads, see Fig. 6. Due to the large scatter of the results, an extrapolation to $N = 1$ (resistance to static loads) results in $\Delta f_{v,Rk} = 0.8$. This only confirms that there is still a need for investigation on screw fastenings under repeated shear loads. In the course of these investigations, extrapolation to larger numbers of repeated loads should also be considered: At the moment, this is not possible due to a lack of data.

5.3 Shear-loaded riveted fastenings

With regard to riveted fastenings under repeated shear loads, reference is made to (10), (18), and (19). Both (10) and (18) have already been introduced in the previous sections in connection with screw fastenings. (19) is the first part of (10), which together deal with a larger research project.

One can certainly also ask whether the behaviour of shear-loaded screw and riveted fastenings is not comparable, so that a joint evaluation is reasonable.

6 SUMMARY

For tensile-loaded screw fastenings, an S-N curve was derived on the basis of test results from the literature and project-specific tests; see Fig. 7. As the failure mode for static and repeated tensile loads is identical, a normalised formulation with a load range Δf_p was chosen. While the resistance to repeated loads from natural wind is sufficiently high, thus confirming established estimates, it can be seen that the fatigue limits for both constant and variable amplitudes are only a fraction of the static resistance. To determine the latter, see (2).

Fig. 7. S-N curve for tensile-loaded screw fastenings of trapezoidal sheeting

For shear-loaded screw fastenings, further investigations are necessary. Apart from the lack of test results, there is a large scatter in the available ones. However, fundamental questions regarding the definition of failure or the specification of suitable test specimens still need to be clarified.

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